

Quality of the used community of practice

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Introduction

Data collection for this study took place within the context of a community of practice (CoP) in which participants reflected on the meaning they attributed to their use of lived experience expertise. Data analysis was conducted using grounded theory as developed by Hennie Boeije. This is a part of a work in progress (a draft monograph); the findings and context have not yet been published.

Andringa & Reyn gave the rules for the used community of practice and Eelderink gave a framework.

3.4 Quality of the research

The quality of the research depends on validity and reliability. As for validity Madelon Eelderink provides a description of participatory action research or PAR on page 23 of her handbook (Eelderink, 2021). Parts of that description can be matched with Andringa and Reyn's ten points. PAR involves a complex problem: all kinds of sub-questions (at point I) of participants with different backgrounds (at III). It is about daily practice and not about something from the past: urgency (at II). The problem with sub-problems is solved jointly: with prioritization (at II) and the group as a whole is responsible for the solution (at VI). It can be viewed from different perspectives: that is the attractiveness of the group (at III). The practice of the group is embedded in a larger system: interaction with one's own practice (at IX). Work is being done towards the desired situation: the sub-questions form the starting points (at I) and development is facilitated (at V). New insights are acquired during the CoP: new things have been done (at VIII). And actions are realised: impact has been made (at IV) and there was reflection on the work (at VII)

It is in line with Doets (1981, p. 133), that the nature of the action research can be considered. And referring to the own input of the researcher in the CoP, for example, method triangulation can be recognized (i.e. a certain phenomenon is investigated with different methods; Van Staa & Evers, 2016). In the latter case, the researcher first led the two responsive evaluations as a kind of assessments and fed the results of those 'assessments' into the CoP. Involving the participants in the course of the research can also be done in the light of Van Staa and Evers's theory, called a form of triangulation. Boog (2016) speaks of 'multi-methodical' as a characteristic of action research.

For internal validity, it is important that the input of participants ne presented as correctly and accurately as possible (Wardekker, 1999, p. 61). At the CoP, a member check occurred at every round, as well as at the establishment of the reports of meetings.

And during the responsive evaluations, the researcher deliberately chose to give as little direction as possible in public publications to what he himself would give meaning to 'experts by experience with other eyes' (Van de Merbel, 2022), in order not to affect the validity of those evaluations: he wanted to avoid that an undetermined number of participants would align their meaning-making with his. He, the researcher, was a participant at the CoP. In this context, Eelderink speaks of the dynamics of the researcher.

As for reliability the researcher has indicated that the selection of participants was partly done by him as a researcher and partly through tips from already recruited participants and through tips of professor Geert Van Hove of Disability Studies (Gent University), that data were collected through a discussion of topics by email and in meetings. The data were analysed using the three-stage coding process.

At the CoP, the researcher managed to contribute to how the ten points of Van Andringa and Reyn were given shape and substance. He also set up a sounding board group, or

supervisory committee (Boog, 2016), to which the progress of the research was presented. Its attitude in itself made the researcher more aware of being able to justify whether he continued to adhere to the method, and the interactions with the sounding board members strengthened that awareness. Consulting colleagues is referred to as 'peer debriefing' by Swanborn (2010, p. 132). This included consultation of the researchers' platform and submission of text to more experienced colleagues.

References

- Andringa, J., & Reyn, L. (2011). *Tien stappen voor een succesvolle Community of Practice* [Ten steps to a successful Community of Practice]. The Hague, the Netherlands: Netherlands Enterprise Agency.
- Boeije, H. (2014). *Analyseren in kwalitatief onderzoek* [Analysis in qualitative research]. Amsterdam, the Netherlands: Boom.
- Boog, B. (2016). Handelingsonderzoek of action research. *Kwalon*, 18, 1-8.
- Doets, C. (1981). *Praktijk en onderzoek. Wetenschap in wisselwerking met praktisch handelen* [Practice and research. Science interacts with practical action.] Amersfoort, the Netherlands: De Horstink.
- Eelderink, M. (2021). *Handboek participatief actieonderzoek*. (Handbook participatory action research.) Amsterdam, the Netherlands: SWP.
- Merbel, L. van de (2022). *Ervaringsdeskundigen met andere ogen: Onderzoeksverslag van twee responsieve evaluaties* [Experiential experts with other eyes: Research report of two responsive evaluations.] Amsterdam, the Netherlands: Brave New Books.
- Staa, A. van & Evers, J. (2016, May 18). *Thick analysis: Strategy to increase the quality of qualitative data analysis*. Retrieved February 28, 2023, from https://www.tijdschriftkwalon.nl/inhoud/tijdschrift_artikel/KW-15-1-2/Thick-analysis-strategie-om-de-kwaliteit-van-kwalitatieve-data-analyse-te-verhogen
- Swanborn, P. (2010). *Basisboek sociaal onderzoek* [Basic book social research.] The Hague, the Netherlands: Boom Onderwijs.
- Wardekker, W. L. (1999). *Criteria voor de kwaliteit van onderzoek* [Criteria for the quality of research.] In B. Levering & P. Smeijers (Eds.), *Opvoeding en onderwijs leren zien* (pp. 50-67). Amsterdam, the Netherlands: Boom Lemma Mens en Maatschappij.